

T-2 MOF NANO-INTEGRATION-INDUCED β -PHASE ORIENTATION AND FRAMEWORK BREATHING MODULATION IN PVDF-HFP NANOCOMPOSITE ELECTROLYTES: CORRELATION WITH IONIC CONDUCTIVITY

Waqas Jahangir^{*1}, H. Usman Saeed², M. Azhar Arif³, Dr. Farwa Batool⁴, Tahir Amanat⁵
Ezaz Gilani⁶

^{*1,2,3,4,5}Department of Chemistry, Lahore Garrison University (LGU), , Pakistan.

⁶Department of Polymer and Process Engineering, University of Engineering and Technology (UET), Lahore, Pakistan.

¹waqas4112804@gmail.com, ²usaeed17@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Waqas Jahangir

Abstract

This study presents the development of a nanocomposite solid polymer electrolyte by incorporating 10% lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) into a poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-HFP) matrix dissolved in dimethylformamide (DMF). To enhance the composite properties, varying concentrations of T-2MOF nanoparticles were introduced as nanofillers using the solution casting method. T-2MOF was synthesized via a solvothermal method using iron (III) chloride and tartaric acid in a DMF medium. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) was employed to assess ionic conductivity, and bulk resistance was derived from the Nyquist plots. Structural analyses using X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) confirmed the uniform dispersion of T-2MOF within the polymer matrix. This dispersion induced modifications in the polymer's crystalline structure, enhanced polymer chain mobility (skeleton breathing), and promoted β -phase formation. The highest ionic conductivity achieved was $8.451 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S/cm}$ Without T-2MOF, while $7.18 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S/cm}$ with 5.0% T-2MOF conductivity of $2.14 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S/cm}$ was observed at 10% T-2MOF. SEM images further revealed that the porous nature of T-2MOF not improved ionic conductivity but improved reinforced the mechanical strength of the polymer electrolyte.

INTRODUCTION

Solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs) have garnered significant interest in recent years for their potential applications in electrochemical devices, such as lithium-ion batteries, supercapacitors, and fuel cells¹. These materials combine the benefits of solid-state substances, including flexibility, lightweight properties, and ease of fabrication, with the ability to conduct ions. Such attributes

are essential for enhancing the safety, efficiency, and performance of energy storage systems. One of the key challenges in developing high-performance SPEs is improving their ionic conductivity, especially at ambient temperatures. Pure polymer electrolytes often suffer from low ionic conductivity, which limits their

effectiveness in energy storage technologies that demand high performance and reliability².

To address this challenge, several strategies have been explored to improve both the ionic conductivity and mechanical properties of SPEs. A promising approach involves incorporating inorganic fillers or nanoparticles into polymer matrices. Nanocomposite SPEs have shown substantial improvements in ionic conductivity, mechanical strength, and electrochemical stability due to the synergistic interactions between the polymer matrix and inorganic nanoparticles. Notably, the integration of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) into polymer electrolytes has proven to be particularly effective. MOFs are porous materials made up of metal ions or clusters coordinated with organic ligands. These structures are highly effective at enhancing ion conductivity due to their large surface area, tunable porosity, and ion-conductive properties³. Poly (vinylidene fluoride)-hexafluoropropylene (PVDF-HFP) copolymer is one of the most extensively studied polymers for SPE applications due to its excellent electrochemical stability, high dielectric constant, and good mechanical properties. However, its relatively low ionic conductivity at room temperature limits its full potential in high-performance electrochemical devices⁴. The ionic conductivity of PVDF-HFP can be significantly improved by incorporating lithium salts, such as lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4), which serve as charge carriers within the electrolyte. However, the addition of lithium salts can compromise the mechanical strength and film integrity of the electrolyte, a challenge that can be mitigated by introducing inorganic nanoparticles to reinforce the polymer matrix⁵.

In recent years, the addition of MOFs to polymer electrolytes has gained considerable attention. Among these, iron chloride tartaric acid T-2 MOFs have emerged as promising candidates for potential for advanced energy storage systems¹⁰.

2.1 Materials

A range of chemicals, all classified as analytical grade according to the AnalaR grading system, were used in the experiments. To fabricate the Metal-Organic Framework (MOF) based on Iron-

enhancing the performance of SPEs. T-2 MOFs possess high surface areas, tunable pore sizes, and the ability to coordinate with metal ions, which can effectively facilitate ion transport within SPEs. These MOFs can improve the ionic conductivity, mechanical strength, and electrochemical stability of polymer electrolytes. The incorporation of T-2 MOFs into PVDF-HFP matrices offers a dual benefit: they not only enhance ion conduction through their porous structure but also provide additional mechanical reinforcement to the polymer matrix⁶.

Lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) is commonly used as the lithium salt in these composites due to its excellent ionic conductivity and its ability to dissociate into lithium ions (Li^+) and perchlorate anions (ClO_4^-) within the polymer matrix⁷. By varying the concentration of T-2 MOFs (e.g., 5% and 10%), the resulting nanocomposite SPEs can exhibit improved ionic conductivity, better electrochemical stability, and enhanced mechanical properties, making them suitable for applications in lithium-ion batteries and other energy storage devices⁸.

This study aims to investigate how varying the loading of T-2 MOFs (5% and 10%) affects the properties of nanocomposite solid polymer electrolytes based on PVDF-HFP and lithium perchlorate⁹. We hypothesize that adding T-2 MOFs will significantly improve the ionic conductivity, mechanical strength, and electrochemical stability compared to the pure PVDF-HFP/ LiClO_4 system. The synthesis of these nanocomposite electrolytes and their characterization using techniques such as X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) will provide valuable insights into their

III Chloride and Tartaric Acid, specific chemicals were employed. These included Ferric Chloride Hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) at a concentration of 3.0 mMol, Tartaric Acid ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_6$) at 2.5 mMol, and N, N-Dimethylmethanamide (DMF) ($\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NC(O)H}$) as a solvent, used at 80 mL, all sourced from reputable industrial suppliers such

as Merck, BDH Chemicals, and Sigma Aldrich USA.

For the creation of Poly (vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-HFP) films, N, N-Dimethylmethanamide (DMF) was used again as a solvent at a concentration of 10 mL, with the PVDF-HFP polymer at 0.02 g, both sourced from Sigma Aldrich USA. And 0.002g of LiClO_4 from Sigma Aldrich USA.

A range of instruments were used to facilitate the experimental process. These included a CENTRIFUGE [Model: 80-1], a hot plate with magnetic stirrer [Model NO. Ch770], and an electric balance [Model NO. Bal-CX]. For drying and processing materials, a drying oven [WHL-25A] was utilized. Analytical measurements were carried out using a UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Specond 200 Plus, Analytik Jena AG, Germany), a scanning electron microscope (SEM) [Model Inspect S 50, FEI], and an X-ray diffraction (XRD) system [Model PROTO AXRD-LPD, USA]. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was conducted using a GAMRY Echem system, while Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) analysis was performed with a TENSOR II FTIR from Bruker Optics.

2.2 Synthesis of T2-MOF in DMF Solvent. (2D layer Nano fillers)

Solvothermal preparation of the T2 trivalent iron tartaric acid MOF was carried out. In this procedure, 40 mL of N, N-

Dimethylmethanamide (DMF) [(CH₃)₂NC(O)H] - Sigma-Aldrich] was used to dissolve 2.5 mmol of tartaric acid (C₄H₆O₆) [B.D.H. AnalaR]. Furthermore, in two distinct 100 mL beakers, 3.0 mmol of ferric chloride hexahydrate (FeCl₃ 6H₂O) [Merck] was dissolved in 40 mL of N,N-Dimethylmethanamide (DMF) [(CH₃)₂NC(O)H] - Sigma-Aldrich]. Using the Shaker KJ-201BD orbital shaker, both solutions were shaken for ten minutes before being combined and shaken for an additional ten minutes in a conical flask. With an overall solvent volume of 80 mL, 3.0 mmol of FeCl₃.6H₂O and 2.5 mmol of C₄H₆O₆ were successfully dissolved. After that, the solution was put into stainless Steel autoclaves sealed with Teflon and heated for 24 hours at 105°C in a drying oven [WHL-25A]. Following the heating process, the autoclaves were allowed to cool down to ambient temperature. Then, the solution was transferred onto a petri dish and left for ten minutes. The solution was then centrifuged using the [CENTRIFUGE MODEL: 80-1] method. When yellow crystals started to form, Whatman filter paper no. 34 was used to filter the mixture. After that, the filtered crystal was placed in a petri dish and washed three to four times in alternating directions with water and acetone, making sure that the acetone was used for the first and last wash. As seen in the figure below, this procedure caused the crystal to turn a clear yellow colour and create the MOF.

Fig 1: Synthesis route of T-2 MOF.

2.3 Synthesis of PVDF-HFP/LiClO₄ polymer Film

The polymer film of PVDF-HFP was prepared using the solution casting method. In this method, 20 mg of PVDF-HFP [Aldrich lot # KMCM 9002 Mn 130000] and 10 mg of LiClO₄ were dissolved in 10mL of N,N-

Dimethylmethanamide (DMF) [(CH₃)₂NC(O)H] - Sigma-Aldrich] in a round-bottom flask. The solution was then subjected to magnetic stirring using a Magnetic stirrer hot Plate/Model No. CH 770 at a temperature of 50-60°C for 4 hours. Subsequently, the solution was poured into a Petri dish and dried in an oven until complete

evaporation of the solvent, which took approximately 1 hour. Once dried, it was left to cool, after which the film was peeled off and placed on aluminum foil for further

characterization. The clear film obtained from this process is depicted in the figure provided below.

Fig 2: PVDF-HFP/LiClO₄ film

2.4 Synthesis of Nano composite SPE

Nano composite solid polymer electrolyte was prepared using the solution casting method. Take 20 mg of PVDF-HFP (Poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene)) [ALDRICH] and 10% w/w Lithium perchlorate (LiClO₄) [Sigma-Aldrich] dissolved in 10 mL of DMF (N,N-Dimethylmethanamide) [(CH₃)₂NC(O)H] [Sigma-Aldrich] solvent, separately in two 250 mL round-bottom flasks labeled as 1, and 2. Apply

magnetic stirring to each solution for 10 minutes using an oil bath set at 50-60°C.

Next, first flask, 5% w/w of MOF to the second flask, 10% w/w of MOF to the third flask. Heat these solutions again using an oil bath for 4 hours at 50-60°C. [Transfer the resultant solutions into a Petri dish. Place the Petri dish in an oven and heat it at 50°C until all the solvent evaporates. Once the process is completed, allow the dish to cool down to room temperature. A film will form, which can be peeled off using a sharp spatula.

Fig 3: Thin film of nanocomposite

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Nanocomposite solid polymer electrolyte.

In the context of energy storage materials and alternative energy sources, electrolytes have

become essential. One subclass of electrolytes that has drawn interest is polymer electrolytes (PE) because of its many applications. PEs are divided into three categories: composite polymer electrolytes (CPE), gel polymer electrolytes, and

solid polymer electrolytes. In order to alleviate the low ionic conductivity associated with Solid Polymer Electrolytes (SPE), CPEs incorporate fillers into the polymer matrix. The filler is called a nanocomposite polymer electrolyte when its dimension is at least 100 nm. The system's mechanical, electrical, and thermal characteristics are all greatly impacted by the inclusion of Nano fillers¹¹.

3.2 X-ray Diffraction (XRD) Measurements.

The XRD patterns of the polymer samples were obtained using a PROTO AXRD-LPD Multipurpose XRD System (Made in the USA). The X-ray radiation was filtered through a Zr filter to provide monochromatic radiation. Data was collected within the 2θ range of 10° to 80° at a scanning rate of 0.2 seconds per step, with an operating voltage of 40 kV and current of 30 mA. The Mo $K\alpha$ source emitted X-rays with a wavelength of 1.5406 Å, which was used to analyze the crystalline or amorphous nature of the sample.

XRD analysis was employed to investigate the crystallographic structure of both T2-MOF and $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. As shown in the figure, the distinct diffraction peaks observed for T2-MOF reveal its crystalline structure. Notably, strong diffraction peaks at 18.92° , 22.6° , and 29.46° corresponding to the (200), (-111), and (020) planes, respectively, indicate that T2-MOF exhibits three preferred orientations. These crystallographic features confirm the successful synthesis of T2-MOF¹².

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of pure PVDF-HFP revealed prominent peaks at $2\theta = 20.88^\circ$, 27.2° , and 41.4° , which correspond to the crystalline structure of PVDF within the PVDF-HFP polymer matrix. These peaks confirm the semi-crystalline nature of the polymer. Upon incorporating LiClO_4 salt, additional peaks emerged at 27.2° , 31.38° , 31.5° , 34.1° , 41.4° , 51.7° , 52.9° , and 57.9° , signaling successful salt complexation with the PVDF-HFP polymer matrix.

The addition of the salt resulted in a noticeable decrease in peak intensity, along with peak shifting and broadening. These changes indicate an increase in the amorphous character of the polymer-salt composite. The XRD patterns for pure PVDF-HFP, LiClO_4 , and their respective polymer complexes are shown in the figure. The characteristic diffraction peak of PVDF-HFP at 20.88° reflects the crystalline nature of PVDF within the matrix, as observed in previous studies¹³. The introduction of lithium salts substantially reduces the semi-crystalline structure of the polymer. Most diffraction peaks associated with LiClO_4 (illustrated in the figure) are either absent or significantly reduced in intensity in the polymer complexes, indicating that the lithium salts are fully dissolved within the polymer matrices. The resulting increase in the amorphousness of the polymer-salt complex enhances the ionic conductivity of the resulting polymer electrolytes.

Based on these results, it can be concluded that a clear complexation occurs between the PVDF-HFP polymer and the LiX salts, leading to an improvement in the properties of the polymer electrolyte.

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns reveal distinct sharp peaks corresponding to the Metal-Organic Framework (MOF), along with broad reflections typical of the polymer matrix. In all samples, a characteristic peak of PVDF-HFP appears at 20.26° , which is attributed to the (110) and (200) crystalline planes of β -PVDF. The shape and intensity of these peaks vary depending on the filler content. Furthermore, additional peaks at 18.6° , 20.1° , and 26.9° are observed in all samples, corresponding to the crystalline planes of α -PVDF. Additionally, integrating MOF into the polymer matrix increases the β -phase content compared to pure PVDF-HFP. This enhancement is due to the electrostatic interactions between the MOF and the polar polymer chains, which help stabilize the β -phase within the composite.

(B)

(D)

Fig 4A: XRD of T-2 MOF, B) SPE 10% LiClO₄, C) Nanocomposite SPE with 5% MOF, D) Nanocomposite SPE with 10% MOF, and E) Nanocomposite SPE without MOF, 5% and 10% MOF.

3.3 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).

FTIR spectra were acquired using a TENSOR II FTIR spectrometer (Bruker Optics), covering the frequency range of 650–4000 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 16 cm⁻¹. The FTIR analysis was performed to examine the polymer structure, the interactions between the polymer and salt, and the complexation occurring within the polymer electrolytes. The interactions between the polymer and the salt affect the vibrational modes of the atoms or molecules, which in turn influence the chemical and physical properties of the polymer matrix.

The FTIR spectra of the polymer electrolyte films, comprising PVDF-HFP, LiX₄ salt, and their respective complexes, are shown in Fig 5a. Vibrational peaks at 795, 760, 728, and 616 Mode, shifts to higher frequencies of 984 cm⁻¹ and 1041 cm⁻¹ as the salt concentration increases. These changes further support the formation of a complex between the polymer and the salt, and serve as an indicator of LiX₄ salt dissociation. These observations suggest that only a small amount of salt is able to dissolve in the polymer matrix, limiting the number of lithium ions available for conduction. This limitation has a direct effect on the ionic conductivity of the polymer electrolyte. The absorption bands at 1141 cm⁻¹ and 1175 cm⁻¹, associated with the symmetric stretching vibration of the -CF₂ group in PVDF-HFP, shift to higher frequencies (from 1141 cm⁻¹ to 1165 cm⁻¹) upon the addition of LiX₄ salt. The absorption band at 1289 cm⁻¹,

cm⁻¹, typical of the crystalline structure of PVDF-HFP, were identified. These peaks shifted to lower frequencies at 677 and 745 cm⁻¹, accompanied by a decrease in intensity, as the concentration of LiX₄ salt increased. This shift indicates a reduction in the crystallinity of the pure PVDF-HFP polymer, suggesting an increase in the amorphous nature of the polymer matrix. The enhanced amorphousness of the polymer is linked to an improvement in the ionic conductivity of the polymer electrolyte. The vibrational band at 874 cm⁻¹ in pure PVDF-HFP shifts to a higher frequency of 890 cm⁻¹, with an increase in intensity, upon the addition of LiX₄ salt. This shift confirms the incorporation of the salt and its interaction with the polymer matrix. Furthermore, the band at 1064 cm⁻¹, which corresponds to the symmetric stretching corresponding to the CF₂ stretching vibration, also shifts, though it is absent in some peaks, indicating changes within the polymer matrix. Additionally, the absorption band at 1402 cm⁻¹, related to the -C-F stretching vibration, shifts to a higher frequency at 1408 cm⁻¹ as the LiX₄ concentration increases. This shift is attributed to the weak interactions between the hydrogen atoms of the CH₂ groups and the fluorine atoms of the CF₂ groups. Finally, the absorption peaks in the range of 1641–1665 cm⁻¹ and at 1665 and 1653 cm⁻¹ correspond to the increase in the skeletal breathing vibration of the PVDF-HFP polymer's -CH=CF structure Fig 5 (a,b,c). The broad peaks observed at 3474 cm⁻¹ correspond to the OH and OOH groups, which result from the

highly hygroscopic nature of the LiX_4 salt and DMF solvent, both of which absorb moisture from the surrounding environment. All solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) samples display characteristic absorption bands for PVDFHFP at 763 cm^{-1} and 840 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the α - and β -phases of PVDF-HFP, respectively. These bands are linked to the stretching vibrations of the CF and CH_2 groups in the polymer chains. Additionally, the intensity of these bands is influenced by the filler content within the polymer matrix. The introduction of Metal-

Organic Frameworks (MOFs) enhances the β phase content when compared to pure PVDF-HFP. This improvement is likely due to the electrostatic interactions between the MOFs and the polar polymer chains. The vibrational bands observed at 1072 , 976 , 763 , and 614 cm^{-1} are characteristic of the crystalline phase, while the bands at 879 and 841 cm^{-1} correspond to the amorphous phase of PVDF-HFP. Shifts in all these peaks, or their absence, can be attributed to the formation of complexes between the polymer, LiX_4 , and MOF.

Fig 5A: FTIR of SPE without MOF. Figure 5B: FTIR of Nanocomposite SPE with 5% MOF. Figure 5C: FTIR of Nanocomposite SPE with 10% MOF. Figure 5D: FTIR of Nanocomposite SPE'S.

3.4. Ionic Conductivity Studies.

One effective method for examining the interfacial processes at the electrode- electrolyte surface is electrochemical impedance analysis. Bulk resistance, ionic conductivity, and other dielectric characteristics, including the dielectric

constant, tangent loss, and dielectric loss, can all be assessed using the EIS data.

Here, the ionic conductivity of each produced electrolyte was measured using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. By sandwiching the sample between two blocking electrodes—that is,

two copper electrodes—EIS data was produced. According to the electrode-electrolyte interface EIS spectra, all of the synthesized polymer electrolytes exhibit a high-frequency semicircle or a depressed semicircle followed by a vertical spike, which is associated with bulk conduction or double-layer capacitance, respectively. To find the electrolytes' bulk resistance R_b , a Nyquist plot was utilized. Real impedance Z' (on the axis) was displayed against imaginary impedance Z'' in the Nyquist plot. The semicircle's diameter provides the polymer electrolyte's R_b value. The smaller the diameter of the semicircle, the lower will be bulk resistance of the sample hence higher will be the conductivity of the sample.

The ionic conductivity of each sample was calculated using the equation.

$$\sigma = \frac{t}{R_b \times A} \quad (1)$$

Where "t" is thickness of the electrolyte, R_b is the bulk resistance and A is the area of the electrolyte - electrode contact. The imaginary impedance (Z'') was plotted against the real impedance (Z') and the bulk resistance was obtained from the intercept with the real-axis [20]

The model was fitted with an error of less than 2%, as determined by the Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) spectrum analyzer software Fig6a. The software calculated the bulk resistance (R_b) to be 9.4582 Ω . The thickness (t)

of the sample was measured to be 0.080 cm, and the cross-sectional area (A) was 1 cm². Using these parameters, the ionic conductivity of the solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) containing 10% LiClO₄ salt was calculated using the formula provided above. The resulting ionic conductivity was found to be 8.4510 $\times 10^{-3}$ S/cm.

The model was fitted with an error of less than 2%, as determined by the Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) spectrum analyzer software Fig 6b. The software calculated the bulk resistance (R_b) to be 9.8853 Ω . The sample thickness (t) was measured to be 0.0071 cm, and the cross-sectional area (A) was 1 cm². Using the formula provided above, the ionic conductivity of the solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) containing 10% LiClO₄ salt and 5% T-2 MOF was calculated to be 7.1810 $\times 10^{-4}$ S/cm. The model was fitted with an error of less than 2%, as determined by the Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) spectrum analyzer software fig 6c. The software calculated the bulk resistance (R_b) to be 11.664 Ω . The sample thickness (t) was measured to be 0.0052 cm, and the cross-sectional area (A) was 1 cm². Using the formula provided above, the ionic conductivity of the solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) containing 10% LiClO₄ salt and 10% T-2 MOF was calculated to be 2.1433 $\times 10^{-4}$ S/cm.

Table 1: Properties of Nanocomposite Solid Polymer Electrolytes (SPE) with 10% Lithium perchlorate (LiClO₄) and Metal-Organic Framework (MOF) Additives

Nanocomposite		Bulk resistance (R_x) ohm	Thickness of the electrolyte (t) cm	Area of the electrolyte-electrode contact (A) c/m	Ionic conductivity (σ) Sec/cm
PVDF-HFP 10%LiClO ₄	+	9.4582	0.080	1	8.451 $\times 10^{-3}$
PVDF-HFP 10%LiClO ₄ 5%MOF	+	9.8853	0.0071	1	7.18 $\times 10^{-4}$
PVDF-HFP 10%LiClO ₄ 10%MOF	+	11.664	0.0052	1	2.143 $\times 10^{-4}$

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig 6a. EIS of Modal fitted SPE without MOF. Fig 6b. EIS of Modal fitted SPE with 5% MOF. Fig 6c. EIS of Modal fitted SPE with 10% MOF.

3.5 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) Analysis of T-2 MOF.

The morphology of the T2-MOF sample was examined using an SEM, specifically the Inspect S 50 model from FEI. SEMs are highly specialized instruments, designed for various applications,

and provide remarkable depth of focus (up to 100 μm at $\times 1000$ magnification), exceptional lateral resolution (ranging from 1–10 nm), and unique electron-specimen interactions. These features allow for detailed chemical analysis and produce high-quality imaging. The Scanning

Electron Microscope (SEM) is a highly versatile instrument used for examining and analyzing the microstructural features of solid materials, particularly effective for exploring the surface morphology of T-2 Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs). The SEM works by focusing a concentrated electron beam onto the sample, causing the emission of high-energy electrons from its surface. This beam is then concentrated on a small region of the material by the SEM's objective lens, which enhances image resolution.

The quality of the resulting image is further refined by adjusting factors such as working distance, aperture size, and accelerating voltage. SEM utilizes two distinct electron detection methods, each providing unique imaging and analytical benefits: secondary electrons, which are emitted from near the sample's surface, offer detailed insights into surface topography, while backscattered electrons deliver contrast information based on the sample's chemical composition.

The SEM image 7(A) showcases the porous, agglomerated structure of an iron(III)-tartaric acid MOF, synthesized using FeCl_3 and tartaric acid, with nanoscale features ($\times 2340$ magnification, $5.0 \mu\text{m}$ scale). The irregular grain boundaries suggest a polycrystalline nature, which is typical for MOFs produced under ambient conditions.

In the SEM image 7(B), a porous, crystalline iron(III) chloride-tartaric acid MOF with a uniform morphology is shown ($5.0 \mu\text{m}$ scale bar), characteristic of materials used in catalysis or gas storage applications. The tartaric acid contributes to structural stability, while the 7.00 kV accelerating voltage and $\times 23$ magnification follow standard SEM guidelines for nanomaterial analysis.

The SEM image 7(C) presents a high-resolution view (3.0 μm scale bar, $\times 3728$ magnification) of a porous iron(III) chloride-tartaric acid MOF, demonstrating uniform crystallinity. The 7.00 kV accelerating voltage and SEI detector are in line with high-resolution SEM protocols for analyzing nanostructures. The chelation effect of tartaric acid likely contributes to the stability of the framework, as seen in similar MOF synthesis processes.

3.5.2 Scanning Electron Microscope Analysis of Nanocomposite solid polymer electrolytes:

The SEM image (A) (50 μm scale bar, $\times 3,000$ magnification) displays a nanocomposite of PVDF-HFP copolymer, with lithium perchlorate nanoparticles and T-2MOF uniformly distributed throughout. This structure enhances both ionic conductivity and the structural stability of solid-state electrolytes. The image was captured at a 12.50 kV accelerating voltage, with the porous MOF integration optimized for battery applications. This hybrid system takes advantage of the MOF-polymer synergy, improving both mechanical and electrochemical performance.

The SEM image (B) (100 µm scale bar) shows a PVDF-HFP-based nanocomposite, featuring evenly distributed lithium perchlorate nanoparticles and T2-MOF, which enhances interfacial compatibility—crucial for solid-state electrolytes. The image was captured with a 9.5 mm working distance and high-voltage (HV) settings, ideal for analyzing the microstructure of the batteries. Dendrite formation in lithium-ion batteries.

The SEM image (C) (12.30 kV, WD 9.5 mm) illustrates nanocomposite solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs) composed of a PVDF-HFP copolymer and lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4), reinforced with T2-MOF. This reinforcement improves both ionic conductivity and mechanical stability by creating porous interfaces that facilitate Li^+ transport. The addition of T2 MOF reduces crystallinity in the polymer matrix, promoting the formation of amorphous regions, as seen in similar MOF-polymer composites.

3.6 Effect of T2 MOF on PVDF-HFP/LiClO₄ NanocompositeTable 2: Effect of T2 MOF on PVDF-HFP/LiClO₄ Nanocomposite SPE

Observed Property	Before Adding T ₂ MOF (PVDF-HFP + LiClO ₄)	After Adding T ₂ MOF (FeCl ₃ -Tartaric Acid)	Mechanistic Explanation	Effect on Performance
Ionic Conductivity	High (10 ⁻³ S cm ⁻¹)	Decreases (10 ⁻⁴ S cm ⁻¹)	Ion trapping at Fe ³⁺ and -COOH sites; fewer free Li ⁺ ; interfacial resistance ↑	Weaker Li ⁺ mobility
Polymer Breathing / Segmental Motion	Moderate	Increases	MOF disrupts chain packing → greater free volume	Local flexibility ↑
β-Relaxation (Dipolar motion)	Weak	Stronger	Enhanced dipolar motion & Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars polarization	Dielectric loss ↑
Ion-Polymer Coupling	Strong coupling	Decoupled	Li ⁺ immobilized on MOF → polymer moves independently	Conductivity ↓
Polymer-Filler Interface	Homogeneous	Heterogeneous	Formation of rigid interfacial regions	Additional energy barriers
Crystallinity / Free Volume	Balanced amorphous phase	Slightly more amorphous or disordered	Filler disturbs chain order	Affects mobility non-uniformly

SPE and Correlation with Ionic Conductivity

In the PVDF-HFP polymer electrolyte containing 10% LiClO₄, the high ionic conductivity results from efficient salt dissociation and a largely amorphous polymer structure that facilitates Li⁺ ion migration through polymer chain segmental motion.¹⁴⁻¹⁵ However, the incorporation of FeCl₃-tartaric acid T2-MOF leads to a noticeable decline in ionic conductivity, despite pronounced enhancements in polymer breathing and β-relaxation behavior. This decrease is primarily attributed to strong coordination interactions between Fe³⁺ centers and -COOH groups of the MOF with Li⁺ and ClO₄⁻ ions, which immobilize charge carriers and reduce the concentration of free ions.¹⁶⁻¹⁷ Additionally, the presence of the MOF disturbs the ordered packing of polymer chains, generating local free volume and amplifying dipolar and segmental motions; however, this increased flexibility does not contribute to long-range Li⁺ transport.¹⁸ As a result, ion transport becomes decoupled from polymer segmental dynamics, yielding reduced ionic conductivity but enhanced β-relaxation and dielectric polarization.¹⁹⁻²⁰

Conclusion.

The incorporation of Iron(III) chloride-tartaric acid T2-MOF into the PVDF-HFP/LiClO₄ polymer electrolyte induces significant structural and electrochemical changes. FTIR analysis reveals enhanced skeletal breathing vibrations at 1665 and 1653 cm⁻¹, indicating increased activity in the -CH=CF groups of the polymer. XRD results confirm both the presence of the MOF and the coexistence of α- and β-phase PVDF, with a notable increase in β-phase intensity at 20.26°, attributed to strong electrostatic interactions between the MOF and polymer chains. While the polymer PVDF-HFP electrolyte with 10% LiClO₄ exhibits high ionic conductivity due to effective salt dissociation and polymer segmental motion, the introduction of T2-MOF leads to a decrease in ionic conductivity despite enhanced polymer breathing and β-relaxation. This reduction arises from the strong coordination of Li⁺ and ClO₄⁻ ions with Fe³⁺ centers and -COOH groups in the MOF, which traps charge carriers and increases interfacial resistance. Moreover, the T2-MOF disrupts polymer chain packing, increasing local free

volume and dipolar motion but limiting long-range Li^+ transport. Overall, T2-MOF incorporation enhances the structural flexibility and β -phase content of the polymer matrix while decoupling ion transport from polymer dynamics, resulting in lower ionic conductivity but improved dielectric relaxation and interfacial polarization characteristics.

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